

SYNTHESIS OF THE DIETHYL ESTER OF AN ISOMER OF THE DICARBOXYLIC ACID (C₁₂H₂₀O₄)—A DEGRADATION PRODUCT OF β -VETIVONE*

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Michael condensation between ethyl cyclopentanone carboxylate and ethyl α -crotonate followed by hydrolysis and esterification furnishes ethyl cyclopentan-1-one-2-(ethyl β -n-butyrate)-2-carboxylate which, on Reformatsky's reaction, followed by unsaturation and hydrogenation, yields ethyl cyclopentane 1-(ethyl- α -propionate)-2- β -n-butyrate.

Pfau and Plattner (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1940, 23, 768) have obtained the dicarboxylic acid (I) through a series of elegant degradative reactions on β -vetivone which occurs in the oil of vetiver.

(I)

(II)

In order to furnish direct synthetical confirmation of the azulene skeleton, Cook and Coats (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 559) have claimed the synthesis of the apo-ketone (II). At the same time we have undertaken the synthesis of the dibasic acid (I), which possesses a comparatively simple structure, along the following line.

Michael condensation between ethyl α -crotonate and ethyl cyclopentan-1-one-2-carboxylate has been carried out in presence of different molecular proportions of potassium ethoxide. The optimum yield of (III, R=CO₂Et; R₁=Et) is obtained when an alcoholic solution of the unsaturated ester is slowly added to the mixture of the β -keto ester and 0.14 mole of potassium ethoxide in alcoholic solution, well cooled in freezing mixture, and the reaction is allowed to proceed for seven days. Due to the possibility of ring fission, which may occur during the above condensation, the use of a comparatively large quantity of alkoxide has been always avoided. Eventually the fission does actually take place to yield (IV) whenever the temperature of the reaction is not kept sufficiently low. Further, time has been found to have considerable influence on the yield of the final product. The condensation product (III, R=CO₂Et; R₁=Et) is hydrolysed with hydrochloric acid to give (III, R=R₁=H) which is rather hygroscopic. The same keto-acid is also obtained from (IV) by means of Dieckmann condensation followed by hydrolysis with 20% sulphuric acid. The ester of the above acid is condensed with ethyl cyanoacetate according to the method of Cope (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 59, 2327) when a poor yield of (V, R=Et; R₁=CN) is obtained. The methylation of the above unsaturated ester has been carried out following Cope and Hancock (*ibid.*, 1938, 60, 2903). The disappointing yield in the Knoevenagel reaction has, however, prevented us from proceeding any further along this line.

The keto-ester (III, R=H; R₁=Et) is refluxed with ethyl 2-bromopropionate and zinc in benzene solution. The resulting lactone (VI) is insoluble in ice-cold 10% caustic soda solution and is resistant to the usual reducing agents, *e.g.*, red phosphorus and iodine; zinc amalgam and concentrated hydrochloric acid (Copp and Simonsen, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 416) and zinc dust and caustic alkali. The lactonic ring has been opened up with phosphorus pentabromide and then treated with alcohol. The bromo-ester, thus obtained, can neither be made to split off a molecule of hydrobromic acid with quinoline or pyridine nor could it be reduced with zinc dust and acetic acid (*cf.* Linstead and Meade, *ibid.*, 1934, 935); but it can easily be converted into the unsaturated acid (V, R=H; R₁=Me) when refluxed with methyl alcoholic caustic potash solution. The diethyl ester of the above acid is hydrogenated over Adam's catalyst and on hydrolysis with alkali furnishes a gummy acid (I) which solidifies after standing for several months. It has been crystallised from dilute methanol, m.p. 129-31°; while the inactive acid obtained by the degradative reaction on β -vetivone melts at 168-69°.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Ethyl cyclopentan-1-one-2-(ethyl- β -n-butyrate)-2-carboxylate.—A solution of ethyl cyclopentanone carboxylate (15.6 g.) in absolute alcohol (33 c.c.) was added drop by drop to the potassium ethoxide solution (metal, 0.52 g., ether 10 c.c. and alcohol 3 c.c.) cooled in a freezing mixture, when a precipitation of the potassium derivative of the β -ketonic ester was observed. Next a solution of crotonic ester (11.4 g.) in alcohol (12 c.c.) was added very slowly to the well cooled contents of the flask with constant shaking. The whole of the reaction mixture became clear and it was allowed to stand for 7 days. The alcohol was removed under reduced pressure and the residue was acidified with acetic acid and diluted with water when a heavy layer separated at the bottom. The insoluble

oil was extracted with ether, washed three times with water and distilled, b.p. 158-60°/5 mm., yield 18 g. (Found : C, 62.13; H, 7.66. $C_{14}H_{22}O_2$ requires C, 62.22; H, 8.14 per cent).

The semicarbazone of the above compound was obtained in the usual way as an oil which solidified on standing for several days and crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 112-15°. (Found : N, 13.3. $C_{13}H_{21}O_2N_2$ requires N, 12.84 per cent).

cycloPentan-1-one-2-β-n-butyric Acid.—The above substituted β-ketonic ester (18 g.) was hydrolysed by refluxing it with hydrochloric acid (100 c.c., 1 : 1) for 16 hours. The mineral acid was removed by evaporation on the water-bath and the residue was distilled, b.p. 154°/4 mm., yield 10 g. The keto-acid failed to furnish a semicarbazone. (Found : C, 63.5; H, 8.2. $C_8H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 63.5; H, 8.23 per cent).

Ethyl cycloPentan-1-one-2-β-n-butyrate.—The above keto acid (10 g.) was esterified with a mixture of alcohol (50 c.c.) and sulphuric acid (3 c.c., *d* 1.84) and the resulting ester was worked up in the usual way, b.p. 117°/4 mm. (Found : C, 66.44; H, 8.82. $C_{11}H_{18}O_4$ requires C, 66.66; H, 9.09 per cent).

The keto-ester furnished a semicarbazone which was crystallised from dilute methanol, m.p. 138-40°. (Found : N, 16.00. $C_{12}H_{21}O_4N_2$ requires N, 16.47 per cent).

Ethyl 2-Methylhexane-1:3:6-tricarboxylate.—In the above Michael condensation when the temperature was allowed to rise due to lack of care or when, immediately after the addition of unsaturated ester the reaction mixture was removed from the freezing bath, either a mixture of (III, $R=CO_2Et$; $R_1=Et$) and (IV) or exclusively (IV) was obtained by working up the reaction mixture in the usual way. The yield of the reaction product (IV), when exclusively formed, was 90%, b.p. 180°/6.5 mm. (Found : C, 61.2; H, 8.4. $C_{18}H_{32}O_6$ requires C, 60.8; H, 8.8 per cent).

Ethyl cycloPentan-1-one-2-(ethyl-β-n-butyrate)-5-carboxylate.—The above compound (IV, 33 g.) was refluxed in benzene (100 c.c.) solution with sodium dust (5 g.) for 3 hours when all the metal went into solution. The reaction product was decomposed with ice-dilute hydrochloric acid, extracted with benzene, washed with dilute sodium carbonate solution and water. The benzene layer was dried and distilled, b.p. 156°/1.5-2 mm. The compound furnished a positive ferric reaction and the colour gradually developed through light green, green, deep green to greenish violet. (Found : C, 62.16; H, 7.82. $C_{14}H_{22}O_6$ requires C, 62.22; H, 8.14 per cent).

The bicarbonate washing was acidified and extracted with ether. The total Dieckmann product (14 g.) was hydrolysed by refluxing with 20% sulphuric acid (60 c.c.) for 24 hours. It was worked up to furnish (III, $R=R_1=H$).

Ethyl cycloPentylidene-1-cyanoacetate-2-β-n-butyrate.—A mixture of the keto-ester (III, $R=H$; $R_1=Et$; 23 g.), ethyl cyanoacetate (13 g.), acetamide (5 g.) and glacial acetic acid (100 c.c.) was slowly distilled from a Claisen's flask provided with a fractionating column, the temperature of the distilling vapour being kept between 112° and 115°. When 95 c.c. of the distillate were collected another portion of glacial acetic acid (55 c.c.) was added and the slow distillation was resumed. After sometime a further quantity of acetic acid (55 c.c.) was collected as distillate when the distillation was stopped. The residue in the flask was cooled and taken in ether which was washed several times with water, dried and distilled, b.p. 163-70°/7 mm. The unchanged

materials were used in a subsequent lot. The total yield of two such condensations was 2.8 g. The unsaturated cyano-ester consisted of a solid part and a liquid portion. Both gave the same analytical data indicating that the two portions are isomerides. (Found : C, 65.06; H, 8.2. $C_{16}H_{21}O_4N$ requires C, 65.52; H, 7.85 per cent).

Ethyl cyclopent-1-or 5-ene-1-ethyl methylcyanoacetate 2-β-n-butyrate.—A solution of the above unsaturated ester (2.8 g.) in alcohol (4.5 c.c.) after cooling for 1 hour in a freezing mixture was added to sodium ethoxide solution (metal 2.5 g., alcohol 9 c.c.) which was also cooled in a freezing mixture for the same period of time. The reaction mixture was occasionally shaken during addition and was allowed to cool for another 1 hour and then methyl iodide was poured into it and the mixture immediately refluxed for 5½ hours on the water-bath. The reaction mixture was diluted with cold water and the precipitated oil was extracted with ether and distilled, b.p. 150-70°/7 mm. The product (2.5 g.), thus obtained, was shaken in benzene (3 c.c.) solution with sodium bisulphite solution (20%, 5 c.c.) for 8 hours. It was extracted with ether, dried and distilled, (i) b.p. 150-60°/6 mm. (ii) 160-70°/6 mm. Both fractions gave the same analytical data. (Found : C, 66.13; H, 8.8. $C_{17}H_{25}O_4N$ requires C, 66.45; H, 8.14 per cent).

δ-Lactone of cyclopentane-1-(ethyl-α-propionate)-1-hydroxy-2-β-n-butyrate.—The keto-ester (III, R=H; R₁=Et; 10 g.) was refluxed in a benzene (25 c.c.) solution with zinc (3.2 g.), ethyl 1-bromopropionate (9 g.) and a crystal of iodine for 1 hour when all the metal went into solution after a vigorous reaction. Then another lot of the metal (3.2 g.), ethyl 1-bromopropionate (3.5 c.c.) and a crystal of iodine was added and the refluxing continued for 45 minutes. Next two lots of zinc (3.2 g.) and a crystal of iodine were added after 1 hour's interval. The Reformatsky's reaction product was decomposed with iced sulphuric acid, extracted with ether, washed with ice-cold 10 per cent caustic soda solution and then with water. The ethereal layer was dried and distilled, b.p. 158-60°/4.5 mm, yield 6 g. (Found : C, 65.98; H, 8.55. $C_{14}H_{22}O_4$ requires C, 66.14; H, 8.66 per cent).

Ethyl cyclopentylidene-1-α-propionate-2-β-n-butyrate.—The above lactonic ester (VI, 8.5 g.) was treated with phosphorus pentabromide (1 mole) and left overnight. The clear solution of the reaction mixture was poured into alcohol (50 c.c.), cooled in ice-water. The alcoholic solution was left overnight, diluted with water, extracted with ether, washed with sodium carbonate solution and water. After removal of ether the crude bromo-ester (8 g.) was obtained.

The crude bromo-ester (10 g.) was refluxed for 1½ hours with methanolic caustic potash (10%, 125 c.c.) and to this solution was added aqueous caustic potash (45%, 20 c.c.) and the reaction mixture was refluxed for 2 hours. The alcohol was driven off and the residue was diluted with water and extracted with ether. The clear aqueous solution was acidified with acetic acid and the precipitated heavy oil was extracted with ether. The ether was driven off and the residue was dried under vacuum and esterified with alcohol (50 c.c.) and concentrated sulphuric acid (5 c.c.). The ester was distilled, b.p. 158°/6.5 mm., yield 2 g. (Found : C, 67.5; H, 9.16. $C_{18}H_{28}O_4$ requires C, 68.08; H, 9.2 per cent).

Ethyl cyclopentane-1-(ethyl-α-propionate)-2-β-n-butyrate.—The above unsaturated ester was hydrogenated over Adam's catalyst (0.1 g.) in acetic acid (15 c.c.) solution and dis-

tilled, b.p. 160°/9 mm. (Found : C, 67.57 ; H, 9.8. $C_{10}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 67.6 ; H, 9.86 per cent).

The saturated ester (0.1 g.) was hydrolysed with methanolic caustic potash (10%, 10 c.c.) and worked up in the usual way. A gummy acid was first obtained which crystallised after 8 months. The acid was once crystallised from dilute methanol, m.p. 129-31°.

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